

Conceptualising the ESG-Performance Nexus: A Theoretical Framework for Indian Banking Sector Analysis

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Abstract

This study will define the comprehensive conceptual framework with the objective of testing the relationship between Environmental, Social, and Governance performance and financial performance of Indian private and public sector banks. On the diverse theoretical frameworks such as Stakeholder Theory, Legitimacy Theory, Institutional Theory, Resource-Based View (RBV), Agency Theory, and Resource Dependence Theory (RDT), the framework discusses the importance of incorporating ESG factors in value creation, regulatory compliance, and the creation of reputational legitimacy. The framework assumes that ESG performance represents a strategic intangible asset that adds to financial performance in the shape of Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Net Interest Margin (NIM) and also aligns with stakeholder values and societal expectations. The framework considers Indian banks' diverse institutional settings, such as variation in public and private ownership structures, and highlights the agency of internal abilities and external pressures in influencing ESG integration. The objective of this study is to develop a theoretically elaborate and empirically assessable model that shapes policy guidelines for ESG disclosure and promotes sustainable banking practices in India.

Key words:- Stakeholder Theory, Legitimacy Theory, Institutional Theory, Resource-Based View (RBV), Agency Theory, and Resource Dependence Theory (RDT)

I. INTRODUCTION

The Sustainable Development Goals promoted by all UN members in 2015, have been instrumental in determining the overall direction of public policies and business strategies (Gonzalez-Ruiz et al., 2024). Goals are primarily grouped into Environmental, Social, and Governance themes. The environmental theme is about minimizing carbon footprints through GHG emissions tracking (Scope 1, 2, and 3), energy efficiency through the utilization of renewable energy sources, and sustainable waste and water management. The social theme is about the well-being of employees, labour rights, diversity and inclusion, and community engagement through CSR. Governance promotes ethical conduct, such as board independence, risk management, anti-corruption culture, data protection, and conservation of biodiversity. These ESG principles lead firms toward sustainable and responsible growth (Kharola et al., n.d.) While there has been widespread investigation examining the relationship between ESG performance and financial outcome in developed economies, there is sparse theoretical insight in emerging market economies such as India, particularly in the banking sector. Indian public sector and private sector banks are increasingly being assessed on the basis of ESG performance. However, the mechanisms through which ESG performance drives financial outcomes. However, the literature is divided with no consensus regarding the theoretical frameworks best representing this ESG performance relationship. Such ambiguity is further compounded by institutional differences between public and private sector banks, which can mediate or moderate this relationship. It is thus an imperative necessary to conceptualize a theoretical framework explaining the ESG performance nexus in the Indian banking sector. Such a framework is necessary to guide future empirical investigation, bank strategies, and policy design in sustainable finance.

The research questions are

RQ1: What are the most appropriate theoretical frameworks under which to explain the correlation between financial performance and ESG ratings for Indian banks?

RQ2: How would a theoretical framework be constructed to guide future empirical research of ESG and financial performance in Indian banks?

This study attempts to theorise the relationship between ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) ratings and the financial performance of Indian banks, with comparative theory-based analysis of both public and private sector banks. This study takes a multi-theory approach—combining arguments of Stakeholder Theory, Legitimacy Theory, Resource-Based View (RBV), and so on—to build a conceptual model for how ESG programmes may be linked with bank performance. The study is limited to Indian commercial banks and does not undertake empirical testing, and hence it is a theoretical contribution building a foundation for future studies. The study has both modern and context-sensitive framework, which is damaged by the absence of validation of data differences in ESG rating methodologies, and changing nature of ESG rules and disclosures in India which can impact the generalisability and persistence of the proposed model.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 ESG and Bank Performance

Many papers have highlighted on how Environmental, Social, and Governance aspects in banking are becoming more crucial to have long-term performance and handle risk. Where as the Environmental efforts, like investing in renewable energy and giving consent towards sustainability, will have a positive impact on financial metrics such as ROA and ROE (Gonzalez-Ruiz et al., 2024). Yet, governance results are mixed often held back by greenwashing and scattered strategies (Alfalih, 2023; Chiaramonte et al., 2022). Research also points out that while ESG integration is strong in environmental areas and okay in social aspects, governance remains shallow leading to a weaker overall effect on bank performance (Palmieri et al., 2024). Taking charge of ESG risk management creates a positive cycle between market value and financial stability in Europe where ESG reputation risk affects stock performance. Material ESG factors—those that matter financially—predict value and resilience better than overall ESG scores. (Bolibok, 2024; Lupu et al., 2022; Mandas et al., 2024). Large banks can handle ESG risks better at their initial stage, but after a expansion difficulty in the governance increases risk (Mandas et al. 2024). Rules and regulations also shape the link between ESG and performance (Aras & Hacıoglu Kazak, 2022; Mohamed Buallay et al., 2023). In other hand the social factors have given a neutral or even negative effect, governance elements like diverse boards and CSR committees can build trust and stability in developed economies (Citterio & King, 2023; Miralles-Quirós et al., 2019). In the end, including important ESG factors improves bank value, cuts down system-wide risk, and makes banks stronger during tough economic times (Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022)

2.2 Materiality and ESG Scoring Tools

Recent research identifies critical issues with ESG scoring systems how they address materiality. Conventional frameworks such as MSCI ESG Ratings examined by (Madison & Schiehl, 2021) too frequently disappoint investors since they ignore financial materiality. To address this, they propose the SASB-Adjusted ESG Score, which reweights ESG pillars to emphasize the critical issues. This is aimed at providing improved evaluations that are more meaningful for investment considerations, with significant focus on environmental considerations. Relevantly (Nielsen, 2023), in 2023 broadens the concept of materiality with "double materiality." This covers both financial effects and societal impacts in accordance with new standards such as the European Sustainability Reporting Standards. This broader concept is required in sectors such as banking where climate risks impact financial stability. Despite such advancements, Garst and others (Clément et al., 2022; Ding & Lee, 2024; Garst et al., 2022) mention that ambiguous definitions and subjective approaches frequently undermine materiality evaluations. This results in unreliable ESG reporting and reduced inclusiveness for stakeholders. There has been criticism of ESG ratings, specifically their focus on financial risks that have had limited strong methodologies and low concordance between rating agencies with a mean correlation value of 60%. (Clément et al., 2022; Ding & Lee, 2024) state the need for industry-specific metrics that are more representative of real-world sustainability. (Wu et al., 2018) also explain the dependence of MSCI on reported data, a preference that is more favorable to large companies while often excluding small or privately owned companies. While there is evidence that suggests high scores for important ESG issues are associated with better long-term performance, standardization and comparability problems remain. Delgado- (Delgado-Ceballos et al., 2023; Nielsen, 2023) call for simplification of ESG tools and inclusion of both financial and stakeholder materiality to better

identify risks and their real-world impact. Looking for a realistic solution, (Madison & Schiehl, 2021) used an automated ESG scoring model based on the SASB Materiality Map to further prioritize important disclosures. Their results indicate that prioritizing important financial and societal disclosures can make stock prices more informative. Finally, many scholars call for a new approach to ESG scoring; instead of focusing on only financial risks, this approach would employ double materiality, increase transparency, and ensure scores are actually representative of sustainability but still useful to investors.

2.3 ESG Shocks and Reputational Risk

The instant problems regarding environmental, social and governance can cause the shocks that can harm a company's reputation, market value, and stakeholder trust. These usually occur when regulations break down, disagreements over societal concerns arise, or environmental catastrophes happen. They stake of the investor trust, increase borrowing expenses, and increase perceived risks are explained by (Mandas et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2023) and demonstrate that stress companies in severe ways. Companies with effective ESG governance when the board is engaged, tend to manage such shocks easier. These companies attract less market penalties and maintain easier access to capital (Akyildirim et al., 2024; Ding & Lee, 2024) Reputational harm plays a major role in ESG shocks. Negative perceptions by stakeholders can destroy trust ruin a brand's reputation and disrupt business operations off balance. (Apicella et al., 2025; Giakoumelou et al., 2022) Companies that emphasize robust ESG governance, prioritize transparency, and develop crisis preparedness usually manage these issues better. They are better equipped to limit financial trouble in the future (Akyildirim et al., 2024; Ding & Lee, 2024) Banks are under this pressure the most because they rely on public trust and compliance with rules. ESG failures in banking can decrease stock prices, instil uncertainty, and change the way financing operates (Murè et al., 2021). Poor ESG performance leads to investors losing trust in how companies manage cash reserves pressuring companies towards conservative money management (Hasan et al., 2022). Conversely, companies that have high ESG ratings benefit from having stronger reputations and maintained investor confidence during difficult situations, which maintains financing more accessible. To address the current information gaps and facilitate corporate progress in environmentally friendly business practices, regulatory authorities are calling for improved business disclosure of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) activities. Future studies will need to focus on the analysis of the heterogeneity of the ESG effects among industries, geographies, and the regulatory regimes that are in place. It is also necessary to understand how ESG ratings affect long-term financial performance (Quang Trinh et al., 2023; Reber et al., 2022)

2.4 Bank Size, Legal Context, and ESG

Bank size has a strong influence on ESG performance. Bigger banks achieve better ESG results because they have more resources advanced systems, and face more public attention. These factors support broader sustainability efforts and better manage risks (Bolibok, 2024; Bruno & Lagasio, 2021; Crespi & Migliavacca, 2020) They gain from economies of scale in ESG practices and earn favourable views from stakeholders, aligning with legitimacy theory (El Khoury et al., 2023; Wang, 2023). But banks with higher net worth managing ESG can become more challenging and which may lead to increasing risks (Bolibok, 2024; El Khoury et al., 2023). In the way the small banks often struggle to adopt ESG because of their limited capabilities, but can adjust fast (Bruno & Lagasio, 2021; Chen et al., 2025). As the way the rules and regulations made an compilation that all banks should adopt ESG and improve transparency (Crespi & Migliavacca, 2020; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022). Large banks operating with strong regulatory frameworks tend to perform well, combining internal assets and external pressure to advance ESG goals (Claudio & Gallo, 2025; Houston et al., 2021). Small banks in less controlled settings may fall behind showing a need for ESG strategies which had to set both the bank's size and its legal surroundings (Chen et al., 2025; Priem & Gabellone, 2000). The link between bank size legal systems, and ESG success is not straightforward. ESG can well improve risk control, stakeholder confidence, and support financial stability over the period of time (Ahmad et al., 2023; Del Sarto, 2025). Future studies should concentrate into these relationships across different regions and regulatory setups to better understand how ESG fits into banking (Neitzert & Petras, 2022; Paolone et al., 2024)

2.5 Implications for Indian Banking Sector

ESG practices, which focus on Environmental, Social, and Governance factors, are being adopted in India's banking sector. Bigger banks, both public and private, are driving this shift because they have better financial resources, technology, and skilled manpower. Their larger scale stronger governance structures, and closer regulatory oversight give them an advantage allowing them to implement ESG policies more than smaller or cooperative banks that struggle with costs and limited capacity (Birindelli et al., 2018a; Purushottam Naidu et al., n.d.; Sharma et al., 2020; Yadav & Asongu, 2025). Study shows how ESG practices build transparency, grow stakeholder trust, and improve competitive standing. However, not sufficient research has been done to study how the size of banks affects ESG adoption across diverse setups in India (El Khoury et al., 2023; Miralles-

Quirós et al., 2019; Yamuna & Priyadharshini, n.d.). Legal frameworks like SEBI guidelines and the Companies Act of 2013 impact ESG reporting for large banks, which have the means to meet these reporting demands. Smaller banks though, might find meeting such requirements tough without proper assistance (El Houry et al., 2023; Miralles-Quirós et al., 2019; Sharma et al., 2020; Yadav & Asongu, 2025). While ESG investments offer strategic and operational benefits critical questions remain unanswered. Areas like challenges in competitive lending, access to green financing, and sector-specific policy actions require more examination (Agarwala et al., 2024; Athari et al., 2024; Purushottam Naidu et al., n.d.; Yamuna & Priyadharshini, n.d.). To ensure banking in India becomes more sustainable and inclusive in the ESG space further research should look combination of factors like bank size, Legal aspects, and types of institutions to know their operational efficiency. This approach could lead to more balanced and effective solutions for ESG integration. (Agarwala et al., 2024; Athari et al., 2024; Birindelli et al., 2018a; Yamuna & Priyadharshini, n.d.)

III. Theories

3.1 Stakeholders Theory

Stakeholder Theory explains that businesses have responsibilities not just to shareholders but to a broader group that includes employees, customers, suppliers, regulators, and the community. This theory fits ESG integration well because it values inclusive choices, trust through openness, and ethical actions. In the banking industry, focusing on ESG factors based on Stakeholder Theory can increase the long-term financial results, which can enhance a stronger reputation, and deepen connections with stakeholders by showing increased Sustainability and the public good (Citterio & King, 2023; Gonzalez-Ruiz et al., 2024; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022). Disclosure of the ESG details of banks will increase the stakeholders' expectations, improve their image, and reduce risks by ensuring transparency, careful planning, and stronger internal oversight (Mandas et al., 2024; Miralles-Quirós et al., 2019; Mohamed Buallay et al., 2023). Considering what different groups can do about it, banks can attract investors who concentrate on sustainability, retaining the efficient workers, and tie their objectives to global systems like the UN SDGs (Alfalih, 2023; Aras & Hacıoglu Kazak, 2022; Birindelli et al., 2018a; Bolibok, 2024). Stakeholder Theory has some challenging issues despite its strengths. Identifying the stakeholder value can feel subjective but not tied to numbers, which makes it hard to work into risk models. Trying to balance different interests might slow decisions and weaken strategies with all the different ESG priorities in play (Mandas et al., 2024; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022). Sometimes, what stakeholders expect does not match up, and it can take a while before reputation gains turn into money. Another issue is that ESG efforts might come off as surface-level more about showing off than actual action. This can hurt trust, grow red tape, and raise costs (Alfalih, 2023; Mohamed Buallay et al., 2023). So, while Stakeholder Theory gives a solid idea for sustainable banking making it work means balancing stakeholder needs so short-term wins do not mess with long-term plans.

3.2 Agency Theory

Agency Theory highlights how essential it is to align the goals of managers and shareholders using methods like performance-based rewards and clear reporting systems. It focuses on reducing the gap in information and cutting agency costs. In ESG matters, it ensures managers stay committed to long-term goals promoting financial responsibility (Gonzalez-Ruiz et al., 2024; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022; Mohamed Buallay et al., 2023). ESG reporting changes the trust by holding middle-level management to responsible for their actions, enhances transparency, and improving board oversight. Governance rooted in agency theory helps lower environmental and social risks that might harm financial outcomes it boots shareholders confidence (Alfalih, 2023; Birindelli et al., 2018a). Agency Theory looks at shareholder value and can also increase the reach of ESG goals in broader contexts. Moreover it emphasis might hold back long-term ESG efforts if they do not provide fast monetary benefits (Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022; Mohamed Buallay et al., 2023). Improve accountability, but it often fails to address conflicts of interest or guarantee successful ESG results. However, measuring ESG performance can be challenging ESG scores fail to represent how complicated a firm's operations are, which might lead to misleading views of its performance. Strict ESG requirements when untied to financial targets, tend to slow decision-making and add unnecessary bureaucracy (Alfalih, 2023; Gonzalez-Ruiz et al., 2024)., Agency Theory provides a way to add ESG accountability through incentives and monitoring, but its effectiveness depends on balancing shareholder profits with broader sustainability goals.

3.3 Resource-Dependence Theory (RDT)

Resource-Dependence Theory (RDT) explains that organizations rely on outside resources like money, market access, and expertise to survive and grow. Regarding ESG, this theory shows that companies with diverse and well-structured boards manage ESG challenges and opportunities more . They draw on broader outside resources and knowledge to do this (Alfalih, 2023; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022). Transparency through clear ESG disclosures strengthens an organization's legitimacy. It reduces over-reliance on a single funding source

and builds stronger connections with key groups like investors, suppliers, and regulators. When companies stay open about ESG-related efforts, they secure important resources in tough times, improve their stock market reputation, and lower the cost of capital. These combined benefits make businesses more resilient and improve their chances of long-term success (Alfalih, 2023; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022). Resource diversity does not follow a simple path. It often complicates finding the right mix of skills and views. ESG investments spark innovation, but they can cost a lot upfront and delay financial gains, as benefits tend to come much later. Theory reminds us that businesses depend on the around economy. When markets become unimaginary or resources become scarce, ESG reporting can become less impactful and cause high difficulty during tough times. Oversharing or promoting ESG plans without proof of success might damage trust in the company. If trust falls, companies could face more scrutiny and lose managerial control, outweighing financial advantages (Alfalih, 2023). While RDT underlines how external resources shape ESG efforts, it also warns against relying too much on uncontrollable factors or making shallow claims without solid backing.

3.4 Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy Theory explains that organizations gain public trust by ensuring their actions and reporting align with society's values and expectations (Aras & Hacıoglu Kazak, 2022; Bolibok, 2024; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022). In banking, this theory highlights the value of acting and to meet societal standards and build acceptance with key groups like investors, regulators, and the general public. Banks that address important ESG issues can increase their reputation, reduce risks tied to environmental or governance issues, and appeal to investors who prioritize social responsibility. These efforts can also lead to stronger credit ratings and better financial performance over time. Businesses seen as reliable and ethical tend to handle uncertain markets more Legitimacy Theory faces a big challenge because it assumes society's expectations are always clear and agreed upon. This idea often doesn't fit well in different cultures and situations. People have different opinions on what "legitimate" ESG behavior means, which can lead to mixed ESG reports or claims of simplified efforts to look good. Without clear and uniform ESG rating methods, comparing how companies perform becomes tough, and it's hard to connect legitimacy-focused ESG actions to real financial results. Meeting society's expectations may improve reputation over time, but it comes with high upfront costs. These include spending money to set up better sustainability systems and improve transparency, which can hurt profits in the short run (Aras & Hacıoglu Kazak, 2022). Legitimacy Theory gives a useful way to study ESG reporting in banking. Still, putting it into practice requires dealing with the clash between varied stakeholder demands and proving ESG efforts create change.

IV Key Concepts and Variables

Different ideas and theories explain how ESG performance links to financial performance in Indian banks. ESG performance examines how banks manage things like carbon emissions and using resources social elements such as employee welfare and community relationships, and governance factors like ethical practices and board structures of the companies . Companies like MSCI and Refinitiv use ESG scores to measure this. Financial outcomes, including measurements like ROA, ROE, and NIM, relate to a bank's ESG levels through things like lowering risks, building reputation, and earning stakeholder trust. The ownership structure, which compares PSBs and PVBs also influences this as each type of bank faces unique governance setups, stakeholder needs, and motivations to adopt ESG policies (Aras & Hacıoglu Kazak, 2022; Bolibok, 2024). Institutional elements like regulations independent boards, and transparency rules encourage banks to apply ESG practices to comply better and stick to Institutional Theory (Birindelli et al., 2018a). According to Legitimacy Theory, banks focus on ESG to meet what society expects and earn public trust. while Stakeholder Theory highlights the importance of meeting the needs of different groups to build trust (Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022). The Resource-Based View (RBV) treats ESG capabilities as important resources that provide higher advantage to the organisation. These together explore how ESG connects with great financial performance in Indian banks and how different ownership models helps organisational setups shape this relationship.

V. Conceptual Framework

With an aim to study interlinkage between Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance and financial performance of Indian banks, a conceptual framework is established based on diverse theoretical visions such as Stakeholder Theory, Legitimacy Theory, Institutional Theory, and the Resource-Based View (RBV). For the purpose of studying interlinkages between Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance and financial performance of Indian banks, a conceptual framework is established based on diverse theoretical visions such as Stakeholder Theory, Legitimacy Theory, Institutional Theory, and the Resource-Based View (RBV). Stakeholder

Theory posits that ESG ratings are positively related to enhanced financial performance, as captured by such measures as Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Net Interest Margin (NIM). ESG performance is posited to be a strategic intangible resource Barney, 1991, which forms the basis of corporate reputation and stakeholder trust Freeman, 1984, subject to the condition that it is aligned with what society expects Suchman, 1995. In the Indian context, differences in ownership structures public vs. private, regulatory policies, and institutional environments have significant influences on ESG disclosure practices and their implications DiMaggio & Powell, 1983. The framework also considers control variables such as bank size, age, and prevailing market conditions that could affect the link between ESG performance and financial outcomes. Further, it theorizes ESG as a rich construct determined by both internal capabilities and legitimizing external influences, arguing that banks with forward-looking ESG strategies are likely to achieve sustainable financial performance (Aras & Hacıoglu Kazak, 2022; Bolibok, 2024; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022). This theoretical framework supports empirical research and adds to the notion of the strategic importance of ESG in India's banking system.

VI. Application of Theory to the Research

This research employs four associated conceptual frameworks Stakeholder Theory, Legitimacy Theory, Institutional Theory, and the Resource-Based View to examine and position the association between Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance and financial performance in the Indian banking industry. These four theories together offer a combined framework by which to explore how ESG activities lead not only to regulatory compliance and the attainment of legitimacy but value creation strategies as well.

Stakeholder Theory, as proposed by Freeman (1984), provides a theoretical basis for understanding the bank's interactions with its various stakeholders, including investors, regulators, employees, and customers. In the Indian banking industry, where there is an active play out of customer aspirations, regulatory requirements, and public confidence, adoption of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices has become increasingly crucial in striking a balance between stakeholder interests and ESG values. Financial institutions that adopt ESG factors, including ethical lending, sustainable governance, and protection of the environment, are likely to exhibit greater ability to drive good stakeholder loyalty, minimize reputational risk, and drive improved financial performance (Alfalih, 2023; Aras & Hacıoglu Kazak, 2022; Birindelli et al., 2018b; Citterio & King, 2023; Gonzalez-Ruiz et al., 2024; Ioan et al., n.d.; Mandas et al., 2024; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2023; Mohamed Buallay et al., 2023; Piotrowska & Piotrowski, 2025)

Legitimacy Theory (Suchman, 1995) explains how banking institutions undertake the communication and enactment of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices in a bid to achieve societal approval and institutional legitimacy. In India, with extensive outreach in public oversight and regulator direction into company sustainability, ESG reporting is a means whereby banks harmonize their operations with societal expectations and norms. Through open disclosure and ethical conduct, banks can enhance their legitimacy, promote investor confidence, and access capital markets (Aras & Hacıoglu Kazak, 2022; Birindelli et al., 2018a; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022; Piotrowska & Piotrowski, 2025)

Institutional Theory, as presented by DiMaggio and Powell (1983), explains how environment pressures—coercive (e.g., regulatory compliance), mimetic (e.g., peer pressure), and normative (i.e., professional norms)—shape organizational behavior in adopting Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices. Indian banking organizations face these pressures in the organization differently. Public sector banks, which are owned by the government, mainly face coercive pressures because they have to comply with government policies regarding sustainability compliance. Private banks, on the other hand, face mimetic and normative pressures, such as compliance with world's best practices and having to fulfill the expectations of investors, that force them to adopt Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices so that they can stay competitive and trustworthy in the banking sector (Bolibok, 2024; Gonzalez-Ruiz et al., 2024)

VII. Conclusion

This study employs a multi-theoretical approach drawing on Stakeholder Theory, Agency Theory, Resource-Dependence Theory (RDT), and Legitimacy Theory to discuss the implications and consequences of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) integration across banks. Stakeholder Theory provides a foundation for explaining how financial institutions address the demands of different stakeholder groups—e.g., employees, customers, investors, and regulators—through participative decision-making practices and

transparency (Citterio & King, 2023; Gonzalez-Ruiz et al., 2024). Agency Theory provides the shareholder-based model focusing on aligning managerial actions with shareholder interests. This alignment is done through the use of performance-based incentive mechanisms and responsibility mechanisms to reduce agency costs while improving ESG performance (Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022; Mohamed Buallay et al., 2023). Resource Dependency Perspective (RDP) also sheds more light by outlining how the activities of ESG can be supported by financial institutions through external resource access, including varied board knowledge and investment funds, that in turn increase organizational flexibility and risk management (Alfalih, 2023; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2022). Legitimacy Theory speaks about the social aspect of ESG and maintains that banks can improve their long-term legitimacy and sustainability by aligning their activities with socially accepted values and making the respective ESG information publicly available (Aras & Hacıoglu Kazak, 2022; Bolibok, 2024). Theory is the underlying basis of the research design by outlining the way indicators related to disclosure and ESG performance are constructed, variable choice, and empirical data analysis. The overall framework provides for a systematic evaluation of ESG practice by considering factors influencing not just financial performance but also issues such as stakeholder alignment, governance controls, resource availability, and legitimacy in society. The research purposeful contribution is extensive which seeks to offer empirically grounded policy frameworks regarding ESG disclosure requirements; enhance banking practice by providing recommendations regarding the incorporation of ESG factors in corporate governance and risk management; and enhance scholarly understanding through demonstrating the benefits of employing a multi-theory framework in the examination of the use of ESG in the banking sector (Aras & Hacıoglu Kazak, 2022; Birindelli et al., 2018a).

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